

- [MESS0004: The Rapid growth of the EPEMC tree](#)
- [MESS0008: MIMS 2.51 - Induction vs. Deduction in MIMS](#)
- [MESS0012: CRH - The Aether Flexion Wave](#)

Figure 1

MIMS 2.02 - Triple-MIMS: the ‘Yahtzee’ of mimsicality is not whimsical, but intentional development of the Self¹

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ABSTRACT

The development of the MIMS philosophy, as a self-consistent philosophy² based on Science first, and then developed in acceleration [under the philosophæther] into a **P⁷ standard**³, to accelerate futurization and research inside of Science, particularly PEMC⁴, is not in a vacuum. It is an example of *triple mimsical development* under an induction-deduction axle, and the rise of awareness or Visualization/Visioneering within the author. This led to an obvious new mimsy (Figure 1), which was *intuited*, and might explain how the altstream ends up in such wildly different places/conclusions (depending on the focus of the individual or group/movement).

Keywords: Philosophy - standards - Science - cosmology - vision - development - awareness - induction

¹ * The comingling and consummation of Destiny, Fate, and CHAOS, as mediated by the Law of Causality, resulting in the actual total Karma (and not merely ‘sins’ and ‘getting what one deserves’) which dictates our results of our causes.

² [MIMS 1.01-.03 - Philosophy Integration Self-test](#)

³ [MIMS 2.21 - MESS0024: Engineering MIMS Philosophy into a Plug and Play Platform \(P7 Resolution\)](#)

⁴ Plasma Electro-magnetic Cosmology

Pre-engineering the Philosophæther (Purpose/P⁸)

In order to work into a higher resolution, the author wants to revisit the following from MESS0025⁵:

Figure 2 - MIMS 2.10.5 - the diagram of the PEMF=UAF analysis; note that the *P* power was/is deeply connected to the What, Why, and How; credit: author

There are many aspects in this diagrammatica that need their own papers. And now we have, finally, an opportunity and reason to delve deep into it; almost an early 2.10.5.1 (within this paper⁶):

- PEM and UF form and other internal 2x2 matrix:
 - Plasma = 0
 - Electromagnetism = -1 (matches “the Force” or *F* power)
 - Unified = 1
 - Field = 0
 - This makes sense in D. Scott’s “force-free field”⁷ model
- Can this exercise work in “reverse” with a forced 2x2?
 - Magnetism = 0
 - Force = -1
 - Field = 1
 - Aether = 0

⁵ [MESS0025: MIMS 2.10.1-3 - Investigation - Sir Arthur's Gift](#)

⁶ For this paper, we are re-instating the virtual philosophical particle of the Realion; which will only exist within the philosophæthereal dimension of this paper.

⁷ <http://www.ptep-online.com/2015/PP-41-13.PDF>

- In this case, it must be taken into account that magnetism is invisible; and the Aether is also; it so happens that we see Magnetism, but we only see the effects of the Aether.
- But it is very hard to understand how the force is opposed to the field; and the force is -1, explaining its connection to the root (-1), since the inverse square law is involved in the Force's measurement.
- As for the Field being 0 and being 1, this could be:
 - Mutual contradiction
 - Law of Polarity on display
 - The covering of all ends by the Field, which is plasmaglyphically connected to the thunderbolts and to The Lord (L power) specifically.
 - A measure of the invisibility of the Force vs. its actual tangibility.
- If→True is a well-known simple test of falseness; it relies upon the axial nature of factual Isness
- False → Then, Else is actually the larger, more relevant axiom of the scientific method, where most hypotheses are proven false, and *then* or *else* more information is sought to determine validity or eventually exterminate the hypothesis.
 - Change Theory is not specifically about the *else*, however, whatever "else" can be said about It All, it changes, and there is always - and fractals mean **always** more "else", whatever the If and Then says about the present, isolated factual pursuit.
- The 5W+H matrix, is an interesting 3x2 matrix for which, in another paper, can be X with the first matrix; in a unique and mimsical way.
 - But here we will devote to the *assumed* associations already made (by the author, in haste, pre-analysis).
 - The rough multiplication is:
 - $$\begin{bmatrix} Plasma\ X\ Who + EM\ X\ When + F\ X\ Why & Plasma\ X\ G + EM\ X\ P + F\ X\ P \\ Unified\ X\ Who + A\ X\ When + Field\ X\ Why & Unified\ X\ G + A\ X\ P + Field\ X\ P \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} -T + Force\ X\ P & -P - F\ X\ P \\ G + T + P & G \end{bmatrix}$$
 - It's safe to say that negative time, in terms of realions, will not exist, and is the Force X Physics conforming to the realion? Unknown. Hard to not see that as 1; which would make it *not* 0.
 - If Physics is taken as real then 0-1 is -1 and that conforms.
 - If Time or God are 1, then we will have a 2; but luckily under Triple Plane Theory (TPT)⁸, G is 1, and nothing else is; so via TPT the theory conforms. If we do not live in a 3D 'holographic' (multi-stream) reality, then the realion contains potentially real data, AND if time is a real æther of time-space, then it is undefined since space is 0 and time would be 1; but we'll just say it's a 1 and that makes the sum 3; and breaks the model. Therefore, we must say that it seems *likely* - philosophically - that $G + T + P = 1$
 - It's also possible the + represent OR, so that if any of them are True, then the total is 1.
 - Let that sink in.
 - $G = A = 0$? Obviously, we see the invisibility aspect, and now we see that God is Heaven and Heaven is God; but can we really accept that $G = 0$?
 - This may break the model.
- Let's arbitrarily set these as such:
 - What = Physics → this is the what will find the Truth
 - How = Philosophæther → this is the method to find the Truth

⁸

- Why = Principles → this is the boundaries and aspect of our seeking of Truth
- How the G power is “where” is apparently solved by the Heaven/Aether issue. Because we never find or see Heaven, we see it as 0, the void, but most probably it is the Counterspace, where all CHAOS goes to be recycled into the order that trickles into the realion through the ‘quantum foam’ of energy; where energy is *information*.
- Why & How ... how does this lead to the D/E/V? We do not know, at this time; and this aspect needs to be revisited in 2.10.5.2

The key to our *new* resolution level, and to install a Plug-n-Play aspect to our shiny new philosophy, is for there to be Purpose. Purpose, more than meaning, gives people a reason to be doing something. They will retroactively install meaning to what went well, not well, in effect ‘what happened.’

What purpose do we find? What purpose is worthy of this philosophy? What purpose, indeed if any, would be worthy of G ☺ D; aka Wu-Tao-Di, the 0 , 1 , 1. Note that if these are all added, instead of fibonacci’d, then you get 2! Note, also, that P + T + G⁹ as the ONE unified field, is 1 + 0 + 1; where Time is Tao; and the polarity of 0 and 1 is now consummated in the ☺. Wu is a homonym for shaman, and five, so we have other, more abstruse plasmaglyphic analysis to do to see if this sound is related to the Force, or Time, perceived as Tao (anciently). The so-called ‘dynamism of Heaven’¹⁰ which is probably related to the physics of the Force, must obviously be related to time.

Also, please note that 0 is the subjective, and 1 is the objective; such that “I” (ego) is 0 and God (reality) is 1 unified everything. Therefore, and with effect, we can understand what is meant by Liu Yiming, when he talks about the Tao of the Changes (the time-flux of events):

“all my doubts disappeared, so that for the first time I realized that the Tao of spiritual alchemy is none other than the Tao of the I Ching, the Tao of sages is none other than the Tao of immortals, and that the I Ching is not a book of divination but rather is the study of investigation of Principles, fulfillment of nature, and arrival at the meaning purpose of life.”¹¹

Let us resay it: what Purpose do we find?

Connecting to the *Light*¹² (Aether in a circuit) as a means to directly repulse the **Darkness** of *nescience* (as a ‘digitized’ value of *dukkha*)

There exists - presumably and according to the author - a circulatory circuit whose energy is not coming from money, sunlight, or a wall outlet, nor specifically from a book/library or even the internet. And to which, if

⁹ Note that G or God is Di; the sound of power. Note also that G and P are swappable, and so set to equals, and we thus know now of God’s omnipotence and source of this omnipotence, within himself; is the axis of 1, alternating around the Wuji-Tao, the yin-yang aka Taijitu. This O is Wu/void, but it is also the axis of the Truth that revolves around itself. Therefore 0 = 1, in that they need one another. But also we see that the arrangement of the Wu-Tao-Di (pronounced as Wu with two De sounds, meaning a one power, is 0+1=1 type situation, and so now we also see that the 2 is also 1, philosophically speaking. The literal “sound of one hand clapping.” Wu is of course, probably a variation of the Ye sound of the sky. But we do not know, at this time. We do now see though, that the word GOD has multilayered holographic verification, including matrix algebra, and requires no validation from atheistic claims. By following a scientific method within this philosophy, born of the scientific method; and collapsed via the realion for physical verification under a Fibonacci code, we have bypassed all the rhetorical nonsense of silly intellects, like Dawkins, for simple mathematical, logical, and mytho-historically codified Truth, behind his or anyone’s ego.

¹⁰ [☰ The 12 Sided Jade Knob](#)

¹¹ Emphasis and change (improvement) to translation is the author’s.

¹² [☰ PEMC OpEd - 10 Reasons Light Cannot be a Particle](#)

one desires fortunes, one will submit and humble oneself, asking for help and surrendering the ego to enslavement and usage of this **Greater Power of Love**, and then one will have this connection. Considering the oddness of the *How*, where the who has been rearranged such that the W is no longer at the front, and is performing this Lord/Destiny/Rotation crossing so that “God” turns over the world... one has to wonder if this rearrangement belies a circuit control mechanism. Does this momentary reversion, inversion, or rearrangement, conforming to the meaning of the word “how”, leads to a discovery of the circuits (presumably), and ultimately a means to eliminate nescience, which the author takes as not to be mere willful ignorance, but anti-science. The “digitizing” of dukkha - ignorant-suffering - is ‘useful’ in that we a) remove the spiritual (ie, Hindu) stigma, and b) by sampling the dukkha into its approximate images of incremental nescience, we can approach the summarized curve but now make the sampling more accessible to the western (ie, mathematical and scientific type).

Now, if we describe nescience in this way, a digitized dukkha that is anti-science specifically and not merely on account of being spiritual, religious, economic, magickal, or other ist, then we can describe the *potential hypothesis* of “connecting to the Light”. In this case, “the Light” refers specifically to this unknown æthereal circuit [;ie, a Dougherty diagram?].

Now, if we define the invisible, the Darkness (or “Fundamental Darkness” as the Buddhists called it) by its antithesis, then we will see that ¹³*all of those that fail to at least attempt* to connect to this Light, are, by their acceptance, permission, activation, complicity, or even advocacy, are belonging to the Darkness. That isn’t to say that those in the Light seek their destruction, but in the end, it is likely true that the nescient will take steps, including leveraged or technological, to extend their feeling or actual potential in the Darkness, to do harm, act as POS, and harm innocents and bystanders. Now, it is true many of the “bystanders” are themselves not innocent and participants, willingly or unwillingly, in the Darkness. Even, perhaps the author. That is why the Light must move as a “self-defense” - or as God would direct - and not attempt to pre-empt the Darkness with specific Darkness. Nevertheless, the Light must, and has historically, been a power source that will use force, even death, to deal with all of the above.

But, is it up to us - individuals - to make these choices, or, without joining a BORG/hive-mind, surrender our egos to the Divine (Whatever that is), engaging in wu-wei¹⁴ (spontaneous non-action), activating this mysterious Atman/Bhagavan aspect of our psyche, in order to further the greatest good with the least damage possible? Obviously, it All circulates back through the great beyond, the Counterspace where all energies resorb and are reconstituted to Order, and this is regardless of our beliefs, permissions, controls, wishes, and ambitions. If the system Can improve, it will; and if it cannot, it won’t; and if it isn’t a matter of improving or not, then it circulates nevertheless without our particular persuasions and identifiers’ modulations!

So one would say, all things being equal, it is better to reduce human (and sure, environmental) suffering than not to. That means doing things responsibly and with accountability, but YES: doing them, and not not not doing them. Farm badly, rather than not at all. Take pharmaceuticals, rather than suffer in the darkness. Own guns for your protection. One day, these things may be less damaging than they are now, but for now, we must acknowledge our failures to see the entire equation, at first, and to make improvements over time. If guns ONLY leveraged bad behavior, then surely the age of duels would have accelerated to deaths daily at every place we go, whenever egos combat. But it hasn’t. That is a media perception that doesn’t match the statistical facts. How long can we put up with a shoddy system awaiting improvement? Unknown. But what is known, or at least demonstrated through this author’s own life and this EPEMC record, its evolution, is that

¹³ MESS0053: Plasma MIMS - fire as a model of the Law of Causation

¹⁴ 無為 “So, the sage acts by doing nothing, Teaches without speaking, Attends all things without making claim on them, Works for them without making them dependent,” taoistic.com/taothemes/wuwei-nonaction.htm

there is an alternative to triple-MIMS development (as shown in Figure 1) that both exceeds the system's limitations and doesn't neglect two axes in favor of only the third one.

EPEMC as a *scientific* Triple-axis development Vehicle

First, let us describe precisely what is meant by the triple-axis, in Figure 1:

1. Spiritual Development - the advancement of the individual possessing an egocentric or self-centered and even solipicistic worldviews towards a **correct** understanding of their relationship to the energetic source of life and power, in the following areas:
 - a. Meaning of life/life's purpose
 - b. Flow of "the Energy" (ka/God's Breath¹⁵)
 - c. Humility
 - d. Free will
2. Career and Social Progress/thought
 - a. Not mere advancement, but enhancement of position, and \$way
 - b. Social thought doesn't mean a mere socialisma, but an expanding worldly view and consciousness, towards - (despite the differences between people, and vast gulfs of opposing views) - an understanding of the Human family, as both a species of DNA, and hopefully, seeing the mutual suffering and enslavement under "the System" as a codependent origination. Everyone sees the career aspect as a matter of mere dollars and cents, so to speak; but it is also a matter of "as a man becometh."
*"When I was a child, I spake as a child, I understood as a child, I thought as a child: but when I became a man, I put away childish things."*¹⁶
 - c. The actual progress of society, measured in average income, freedom access, resource access, and infrastructure integrity, as well as the **true advancement** of ideals, without backwardsness, not only in terms of bigotry (legally speaking) but also in morality and moral measures, ethics, and actual - individual - justice.
3. Mystery/Secrets Awareness
 - a. One of the ways that people truly grow, is not memorization of school conformed data, but engagement of the 'childlike' mind with the Great Mystery around us at every moment. Indeed it is the spirit of science itself; and of every scientist, even if they prefer cataloging to understanding. The "right name" of things is as magickal as the reality of how it works, and why.
 - b. Secrets, whether they are spiritual, financial, governmental, conspiratorial, or anything else are intriguing, and people will chase them, almost regardless of their safety or quality.
 - c. Being simply aware is of its own benefit, but being aware of how to use the awareness is also of grand benefit.
 - d. Being capable of uncovering secrets is merely a matter of openness. Being able to handle the information and how to live/what to do afterwards is its own secret wisdom.

Now, suppose that you want to develop all of them simultaneously. Where are there safe, adequate, competent vehicles? MIMS to help you develop in all three, to get where you want to get to?

¹⁵ MESS0030: PNR - The Breath of God and the 3 Pure Ones

¹⁶ 1 Corinthians 13:11

Table 1 - Viability of the MIMS for each of these random areas

	<i>Spiritual Development</i>	<i>Career/\$ocial Development</i>	<i>Mystery/Secret Awareness</i>
Primary school	Gray	Red	Yellow
High School	Gray	Yellow	Yellow
College	Yellow	Green	Orange
Corporate ladder	Red	Green	Yellow
Factory work	Red	Yellow	Gray
Agriculture	Green	Red	Yellow
Church and temple, etc.	Orange	Yellow	Red
Cults like Scientology	Yellow	Yellow	Orange
Independent Cults	Red	Yellow	Orange
Military service	Red	Orange	Gray
EMT, fire, policework	Green	Orange	Gray
Ranger/service	Yellow	Yellow	Green
Engineering	Yellow	Orange	Green
Financial services	Red	Green	Red
Librarian	Yellow	Red	Green
Monk, nun, seeker	Green	Gray	Green
Climber or guide	Gray	Orange	Orange
Doctor or Surgeon	Yellow	Green	Orange
Therapist	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
Alternative Healer	Green	Orange	Green
Astrophysicist	Gray	Green	Orange
EPEMC	Yellow	Orange	Green

Gray-n/a; Green-typically excellent; Yellow-typically mediocre; Orange-Should be much better; Red-typically an anti-MIMS

Looking at the above we can see that many different career and social areas are dubious MIMS. EPEMC, likewise is not *yet* a proven career or social progressor, although yes there is evidence. As for spiritual development, it is not specifically designed for that; but with foundations in MIMS and "Parameterizing

the New Religion,”¹⁷ it has at least the foundations to make the fantastic differences that *should* be afforded by a very excellent cosmology.

Money MIM\$ - the appropriateness of currency in \$cience and other platform developments

Money, in its basic energetic form, is a MIMS. It is a great, stable store of previous effort and acts as a fairly quick lubricant to human interactions; albeit a bit incendiary and even volatile. Chemistry-wise, the use of money - for just about everything - is highly questionable. Consider it from a cooking perspective. It is not *always* appropriate to use oil, or sugar, or flour. So applying capital to science or medicine, for example, is not always a good idea; or a scientifically appropriate idea. Take the classic example of cigarette money for cigarette research. An obviously bad idea? Apparently not to most, because guess who does vaccine and drug research? Drug companies. Who does energy research? Energy companies. Who does nuclear research? Nuclear labs. Who does genetic and biological research? Biolabs. See the double standard? If we know that cigarette companies and other firms of the 50s, from plastic to food additive chemicals, did scientifically dubious, biased, padded, or fraudulent research, what should we expect from companies with 10x or 100x that type of capital injection, with almost very little regulation or oversight? And why would there be **real** oversight? Again, we know money's property as a lubricant. It greases palms and makes people slimy.

But yet, we need many forms of platform development, including within and from EPEMC, MIMS, Strategy Series, SPACERS, AIM, etc. in order to continue to improve mankind's situation. We are not going backwards to a tribal, primitive technological platform, no matter what off-grid preppers want. It isn't because that's a bad way to live, it's clearly superior. But, it is not scalable to the 8 billion lives presently in need. Look at Africa. It is an environmental and resource-laden wonderland, but the richest regions are either mined or protected, leaving billions in squalor and disease-riddled poverty.

Therefore, it's absolutely imperative that we consider the means to use money appropriately, ethically, even morally, and with the restraints of controls. We should cease thinking of the use of money from the point of view of negativity only, or an upturning of our noses. Instead, we should focus on safe, reliable use just as we would with sulfuric acid, acetone, or any other important chemical.

The Threefold Science¹⁸ [in Philosophæthereal terms]

In previous work, the author spoke of the MIMS of the Threefold, or True Science, where Supreme, Secret, and Sacred sciences act as a three-dimensional (not geometrically) means of examining the realion, and the entire TPT model, but through mytho-historically practiced means. Examples include martial arts, fengshui, and astrology; but typically speaking alchemy is the top. The entire second part is devoted to mimsically expressing this TS/TFS into a modern conveyance.

But this was written prior to the codification of the P⁷ resolution, which is now augmented with the concept of Purpose, which is (of course, and naturally) powered by the who, where, why, what, when, and how.

Now, can these three dimensions, or “Wings” of scientific endeavor be mapped overtop of the Triple-MIMS, as described? Well, not exactly. It's best, actually, to create a map that is more than a mere Vinn diagram, but an actual tapestry of meaning and utility. If this is then mapped alongside the EPEMC, as an array of arrays, perhaps a utility will become obvious. But, the author has never done this before, so it's also possibly

¹⁷ Parameters for New Religion

¹⁸ MIMS: The threefold Sacred Sciences

specious. Therefore as a warning: there is nothing expected here, but it might, regardless become useful information, regardless. Doubtfully, it would likely interact with the work on the 2X3 and 3X2, earlier.

Table 2 - Triple-axis vs. Threefold Sciences

	<i>Spiritual Development</i>	<i>Career & \$ocial Dev'p</i>	<i>Mystery/Secret Awareness</i>
<u>Supreme Sciences</u>	Ideal	Generally Ideal	Ideal
<u>Sacred Sciences</u>	Very Ideal	Somewhat Ideal	Generally Ideal
<u>Secret Sciences</u>	Somewhat unideal	Ideal	Very Ideal

Luckily, none of the above are Unideal to Very Unideal, or we would have a serious problem. Obviously, as mentioned in the Secret Sciences section of that paper, these can be unideal when they lead the person away from God (as they pursue their own personal power, or even ultimate power), and even destroy their souls and spirits.

Making the “True Science” the Mainstream

The Altstream will always be alternative; however, it isn't necessary for the True Science - the type practiced by the Gilberts, Galileos, Newtons¹⁹, and Teslas of the world - to itself be alternative. It can, and with the proper seizure of the codes of reality and power, via the Axioms of Power, Influence, and Access, lead the present alternatives, which are more mimsical than the mainstream, into the mainstream. One way this happens, is a grassroots use of virality, such as the news about positive effects (even miraculous) of healthy, alternative lifestyle choices. Another is by appealing to the lowest common denominators of biological bias, entertainment, luxury, hope, and even materialism.

So, how can we obtain these codes, these rights, these 'powers' over language, law, money flow, and affluence, if they are locked away by the rich and powerful, and their acolytes and lapdogs? In a fascist POS society, how can we circumvent that? It isn't merely by hoping, or blind faith in the power of love, or anything so hippy-dippy. It is by giving credence to the powers that are protective, within the Human Spirit that hope and endeavor enable *imagination* and *innovation*.

But, as usual, there are rules. There cannot be pure imagination without the restraint/constraint of responsibilities, truth, ethics, etc. There has to be a general gestalt of guidance if not outright control. But with the imagination, there is the possibility of creation and destruction, of mercy or wanton escalation of anything widely considered negative, bad, or evil.

To do this, the MIMS of media, of games/play, of books and audiobooks, of art, etc. need to be utilized in wide parameters, within reason and not outside the viability of life, and mutual fellowship. If that mutual fellowship - or at least at a minimum tacit tolerance - is lost, then what results is social chaos, or madness. It is the death of civilization itself. Ergo, it is important that all the flow of new, mimsical information, that comes into the true seekers of the altstream and forefronts of unsanctioned science, overcome the morass and inertia of the 'fatcat' mainstream, the “settled science” POS purveyors, who are (quite literally) in bed with powerful corporate interest\$, and which impede progress and civilization. Without this, then society **simply dies**.

¹⁹ [MESS0033: Sir Isaac Newton - the Opti-Mystic](#)

The Origins vs Exits (ie, Birth and Death); in Increasing Human Energy *theme* of Nikola Tesla, the opti-mystic²⁰

Tesla, more than anyone since Sir Newton, was an opti-mystic, connected to the Light. He **saw** his sciences and inventions *before* he built them; and with limited modification he was able to implement them. In fact, he was able to precognate the highlights of the 20th century in 2 pages of his autobiography²¹:

- Teleautomatons - Robots & artificial intelligence
- Wireless telegraphy - Cellular and wifi
- Missile weapons - ICBMs
- Unlock the power of the atom - 24 years before Manhattan Project

The truth is that no one knows the inflow particulars of a life; or the exact, precise details of the outflow procedures of a death. We only have various levels of faith, from scientific to semi-scientific to pseudoscientific to superstitious and outright blind faith. But, there have been indications, and there are logical deductions, as well as the limited but sometimes mimsically reliable natures of ancient religions (ie, archaic, pre-scientific philosophies). The tops of these are:

- ❖ The Bible
- ❖ The Tibetan Book of the Dead
- ❖ The Egyptian Book of the Dead

How can we get at these caches of information, save through an engineered philosophy and particular abstract and abstruse technologies that mimsically *hack and attack* Darkness. Not with aggression, but an insistent tenacity of scientific rigor, like ole Tom Edison did with the light bulb, refusing to give up. We don't need to become arcane necromancers, or worshippers of the Womb (in service to an obsession with the Atom egg of the prehistoric past). We only need to be methodical, follow the alchemy of enriching and reality mining, and dissect the realion.

What are the known parts of particles? The known typical characteristics?

- | | |
|-----------------|---|
| | Realion? |
| ➤ Spin | how we see our collapsed wave-function (our time sense of real now) |
| ➤ Charge-weight | the energetics of the situation; its 'gravity' or a person's 'gravitas' |
| ➤ Determinant | the vector of the realion, with its magnitude factored; the 'moment' |
| ➤ Up or down | See Figure 1, and examine a life ²² . |
| ➤ Exclusivity | A singular, crystalized moment, never seen before or again? |
| ➤ Wavefunction | ie, the timestream, not as a mere passage of events, but a vibration |
| ➤ Symmetry | Or lack thereof; ie randomisty (the jiggle of the PPPC ²³). |
| ➤ Pressure | The gradient of the real moment, which exerts <i>Influence</i> on the karma ²⁴ |
| ➤ Entanglement | The interwoven connectivity (The Light) between Up or Down phwarks |

²⁰ [MESS0033: Sir Isaac Newton - the Opti-Mystic](#)

²¹ <https://www.pdfdrive.com/my-inventions-the-autobiography-of-nikola-tesla-e158009062.html>

²² "There is a way which seemeth right unto a man, But the end thereof are the ways of death." ~ Proverbs 14:12-13

²³ [MIMS - The Big G of 5 Forces](#)

²⁴ "Sho ho jisso, sho i shoho, nyo ze so, nyo ze sho, nyo ze tai, nyo ze riki, nyo ze sa, nyo ze in, nyo ze en, nyo ze ka, nyo ze ho, nyo ze honmak kuykyo to." ~Lotus Sutra Chapter 2

It means "this reality consists of: Appearance, Nature, Entity, Power, Influence, Inherent Cause, Relation, Latent Effect, Manifest Effect, Consistency, From beginning to end"

These phwarks, are merely proposed philosophical, ie virtual philosophical sub-particles, which are natural outflows of this form of inquiry. There is no way of knowing if the phwark which exists within a present real moment - within our realion we are attached to as a 'forever' now, in our nescience and short-sightedness - is up for up's sake, or down for down's sake. In fact, it is relative one to the other. You only know if a person's moment is arriving by another's departure. You only know success from failure. You only know good from evil.

Conclusionary Thoughts

The conclusions, naturally, from any speculation must be (at best) inconclusive. "More research necessary" is the bane of philosophers and scientists, alike. Only, in the instance of MIMS we have a scientific philosophy made by an engineer mindset. Think about the factuality of most philosophical history. It mostly came from the egos of bright, but frequently misguided intellects. The author doesn't pretend to have the intellect of a Nietzsche, or Zhuanzi, etc. Historical persons prior to the computer age, and to the sciences of Operations Research and Data Analytics, cannot be held terribly liable for their reliance on bad data, or conjecture. Before Galileo they cannot even be held liable for their reliance on superstition. And yet, the author has shown, even recently, that there are minings of reality data that remain within archaic thought systems, such as Taoism, Buddhism, Chinese medicine, Chinese astrology (which is based on time post cataclysm), Mayan calendrics, rock art, etc.

What is key to understanding this line of inquiry is the very idea of the membranous interface of material and spiritual philosophæther. The interchange between reality (as the material, 3D spectrum), and the spiritual (as not mere consciousness, but the powers, principles, and the A power, etc.) is the particular subject of this philosophy, but always with a goal of futurization, leverage, or levered knowledge, and >>improving the world<<. The author must re-emphasize this about the P⁸ resolution, no matter the flavor of philosophæther favored by the reader, or philosopher. If the world is not to be improved, then it cannot be mimsical, but must be anti-mimsical, even if it borrows perfect knowledge from the future in a 100% leveraged manner. The entire point of this philosophy is to improve humanity, and the world. Otherwise, it is simply prognostication gone amok.

As for the "what's next" of this line of inquiry, now that we have 'smashed' open our realion philosophical particle... the author imagines that there will be at some point a logical and philosophical, perhaps melancholic-like sojourn into the phwark, and to explore the truthiness of the particle values. If, in fact, the real moment, crystalized for us in the extreme of a single PPC windowed experience, distilled into 100% probability, with pure exclusion of all other possibilities and potentialities, consists of a G=0 phase, or that $1 \text{ or } 1 = 1 + 1 = 2$, where $0=1$ and Time is Tao... isn't it possible that we might find within that brief, impossible-seeming realm, a moment of Truth? If that moment of Truth is T⁴, with taran²⁵ (thunderbolt or power) as its proxy wrapping, then what profundity does the measure of the Force take? If God - the Lord - as it was seen was the thunderbolt, or even the thunderclap, and a sound, then we are left to wonder at the sheer impossibility that such a simple thing can produce all of this spiritual, emotional, and material outpouring from mankind, without a deeper, resonant source beyond it. In other words, the seal of authority of the Lord in the T sound, might be the limited exposure we have to a greater Truth. In which case we begin to also understand the profundity - **ProFunDiTy**²⁶ - of the zen-like moment absorbed in the realion concept. That there is, beyond all possibility, an existing remote access of the deepest meanings of purpose, and life, contained within the sound of the Force enacting, and it has the same meaning as the motion of electrical charge, for they are the same generalized connection. But,

P	D
F	T

²⁵ Uchell (High Lord) vs Shang Di

²⁶ Two powers, relating to the two sounds, all relating to the "Thunderbolt of the Gods."

what differs is, from our limited perspectives, the vagaries of opportunity that come from chaotic moments, where fluid reality is not yet collapsed into such a situation as 100% probability. What we call Fate inevitably we rely on past measurement. Yet, we know the past and the future is lossy. So the moment is being lost ere it is measured, properly. The escape, therefore, of certitude reminds us of the very assurances we have about death, Heaven, or God. We know we will die, just as we know we were born. But there isn't much certitude outside of that. Isn't that fickle and arbitrary? Of course it is, and that very might well be the point, depending on the line of inquiry or perspective. Perhaps there is a Dynamism of Heaven²⁷ that relies upon gradient of ignorance, even nescience, which is violated by these proceedings and the preceding. It might even be that the entire pursuit of the philosophæther is doomed to failure by design. But if dreams can be prophetic, and they are - in essence - financially worthless... then why cannot the inquiry be at least productive, if not treasure-laden? Why only rely on the genuine spiritual moment for spiritual progress? Why not, instead, embrace a more rounded view of EPEMC, where the extension envelops the MIMS, in an embrace directly of the above-stated goals? But also let it envelop the inquiry into metaphysics and semi-sciences... This, some would argue has already happened and would continue, unchecked, and worsening.

Figure 4 - particle smashing; credit: Nesbyte²⁸

That's an unfair characterization, since after all, the foundations of this philosophy has attempted to be self-consistent and couched/measured against something larger, more real, and mytho-historically based! In the end surmise, the bias of the reader (or shortcomings in terms of reading and critical thinking skills) will determine if the endeavor,

in sum total, is fluff and BS, a waste of time, or quite productive as a MIMS itself in the areas mentioned. Not only in pursuit of the abstract and philosophical, the mysterious... but also finances, education, medicine, and more. So far, while not perfect nor complete, the MIMS philosophy has done just these things, or remains on the early brink of a breakthrough. Note that the PEMC community at large is only beginning to take note of the Plasma Petroglyphs paper, and yet is therefore in the first iteration of EPEMC, while we are (Dear Readers!) completing the third iteration, and ready to being the fourth phase, already at the cusp of financial explosions. And these, despite the sabotage of the author by the defunct, decaying codes of the cryptocurrency world!

Still, let us stay sober in all further inquiries. Smash virtual particles if you must. But try out, first and foremost, the connections to The Light. *"Forth, and fear no Darkness!"* ~King Theoden

²⁷ [MESS0037: MIMS 2.801 - the Eight Domain Array](#) Appendix.

²⁸ <https://discover.hubpages.com/education/A-Guide-to-Subatomic-Particles>

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